

MORPHOLOGICAL METHODS AND ETHICAL NORMS FOR HANDLING EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS IN SCIENTIFIC STUDIES

Mekhriddinov M.K.

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5021-0029>

Bukhara state medical institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17865397>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07th December 2025

Accepted: 08th December 2025

Online: 09th December 2025

KEYWORDS

To determine the role of destructive pneumonia in respiratory system diseases.

ABSTRACT

Despite the achievements of modern medicine in the field of pediatric surgery, the early diagnosis and treatment of destructive pneumonia remain an urgent problem. Among infectious diseases in children, pneumonia is still considered the most widespread pathology. Despite ongoing vaccination aimed at preventing pneumonia, the mortality rate among children and infants due to pneumonia and its destructive complications remains significant [1,4]. Currently, acute destructive pneumonia is considered a severe purulent-septic disease that occurs as a complication of pneumonia in children. The current relevance of the disease lies in its incidence across all age groups of children, accompanied by purulent inflammation in the lungs and pleura. At the same time, there are certain problems in its prevention, diagnosis, and treatment processes [2,3,5,6]

Relevance: Despite the achievements of modern medicine in the field of pediatric surgery, the early diagnosis and treatment of destructive pneumonia remain an urgent problem. Among infectious diseases in children, pneumonia is still considered the most widespread pathology. Despite ongoing vaccination aimed at preventing pneumonia, the mortality rate among children and infants due to pneumonia and its destructive complications remains significant [1,4]. Currently, acute destructive pneumonia is considered a severe purulent-septic disease that occurs as a complication of pneumonia in children. The current relevance of the disease lies in its incidence across all age groups of children, accompanied by purulent inflammation in the lungs and pleura. At the same time, there are certain problems in its prevention, diagnosis, and treatment processes [2,3,5,6].

Research aim: To determine the role of destructive pneumonia in respiratory system diseases.

Research methods and methodology: Taking into account the various principles of modern scientific knowledge, we developed our research methodology to adequately address the stated objective. The planned and conducted studies, based on general scientific and specific methods, were aimed at solving the posed tasks.

Research results:

Humanity has increased its knowledge and experience by observing changes in the environment, including studying the behavior of wild animals, and drawing certain

conclusions. With the advancement of science and technology, including modern medicine, there is a great need and widespread use of laboratory animals to study the etiopathogenesis, course, and treatment of diseases. When conducting scientific research with these animals, it is necessary not to deviate from certain humanitarian principles [1, 4, 10].

The ethical standards for the use of laboratory animals include the principles of reducing the number of animals in research as much as possible, optimizing their use, and replacing them with other testing methods where possible (the **3R principle**), as well as ensuring their welfare. Key requirements include humane treatment, minimizing pain and stress, providing comfortable living conditions, ensuring that the research aligns with an approved scientific purpose, and training and improving the qualifications of personnel. All researchers must be proficient in working with laboratory animals, and surgical procedures should be performed by an experienced anesthetist [1,3].

The necessity and efficacy of procedures performed on animals for science or medicine must be proven. It must be ensured that the use of animals yields high efficiency. The principles of working with these laboratory animals are regulated by international and national legislation [1,2,4].

Conclusions:

1.The use of laboratory animals in modern medicine and science to study the etiopathogenesis, course, and treatment methods of diseases is a necessary requirement. However, this process must be carried out based on strict ethical standards and humanitarian principles (minimizing pain and stress) founded on the "3R principle" (Reduce – decrease the number, Refine – optimize conditions, Replace – substitute with another method). These principles are regulated by international and national legislation, which demands high qualifications and responsibility from research personnel.

2.White laboratory rats (WLR) are widely used as the main experimental animal in biomedical research, including modeling respiratory system pathologies (COPD, fibrosis, emphysema), due to their fast metabolism, simplicity, non-aggressiveness, and cost-effectiveness. However, the lack of sufficiently complete data in the literature regarding pathomorphological changes in the dynamics of experimental pulmonary-pleural inflammation creates doubt about the legitimacy of correctly extrapolating the obtained experimental results to human clinics. Therefore, collecting accurate morphological data remains an urgent scientific task

References:

- 1.Петренко В.М. Морфогенез в эволюции. Элементы сравнительной анатомии. – Берлин: Директ-Медиа, 2019. – С. 48-56.
- 2.Петри А., Сэбин К. Наглядная медицинская статистика. Пер. с англ.; под ред. В.П. Леонова. – М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2021. – 232 с.
3. Раджабов А. Развитие и микроскопическое строение предстательной железы крыс в раннем постнатальном онтогенезе // Профилактическая медицина и здоровье. – 2024. – Т. 3, №5. – С. 18–27.
- 4.Разин М.П., Аксельров М.А., Минаев С.В., Дьяконов Д.А. Клинико-микробиологические параллели гнойно-септических заболеваний у детей // Медицинский альманах. – 2019. – № 5-6. – С. 62-65.

Б.Разумовский А.Ю., Аллаберганов К.А., Алхасов М.Б. и др. Торакоскопические операции при буллезной форме гнойно-воспалительных заболеваний легких у детей // Детская хирургия. – 2006. – № 5. – С. 4-5.

